

InGEPaST project

“The Intersection of Gender and Ethnicity in Socio-Economic Participation in South Tyrol and Catalonia in Post-Pandemic Times”

WP1 – Deliverable D.1.1
“Research Data Management Plan”
March 2022 (month 3)

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Bando di promozione della mobilità internazionale di ricercatori e ricercatrici
funded by the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen
Decree: 20771/2021 - CUP: D55F21004120003

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6531621

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1 Overview of the project

Name of project	The Intersection of Gender and Ethnicity in Socioeconomic Participation in South Tyrol and Catalonia in Post-Pandemic Times - InGEPaST
Name of researcher	Dr. Alexandra Tomaselli (PI)
Description of the project	<p>Abstract</p> <p>The InGEPaST project aims to explore the intersection of gender and ethnicity vis-à-vis socioeconomic participation in two substate units that share similar autonomous settings and societal challenges (South Tyrol and Catalonia) to provide innovative solutions for enhancing the access to employment, education, and social and public services of women and LGBTIAQ+ (lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, gender diverse, intersex, asexual, queer and questioning) individuals in a post-pandemic scenario.</p> <p>InGEPaST's main hypothesis is that the adverse effects of the intersection of gender and ethnicity (particularly, in terms of socioeconomic participation, i.e., access to employment, education, and social and public services) have recently worsened vis-à-vis women and LGBTIAQ+ individuals due to both the pandemic and the precautionary safety measures (e.g., lockdowns, homeschooling, prohibition of gatherings) also in rich areas such as South Tyrol. Therefore, there is a need to understand how this intersection operates and relates also with other social drivers (i.e., social conditions and factors; e.g., age, class, domestic division of labor, degree of agency, religion, stereotypes, urban-rural reality, violence).</p> <p>InGEPaST adopts an interdisciplinary socio-legal approach and a qualitative methodology. It thus works with the real-world gender policies' stakeholders (women and LGBTIAQ+ individuals and their associations) as well as local policymakers by conducting empirical research in both South Tyrol and Catalonia. Its outputs include not only solid scientific results but also a set of policy indications in the field of socioeconomic participation in South Tyrol.</p> <p>InGEPaST proposes an applied research approach that innovatively bridges three areas of study (gender, minorities/stateless nations, and migration) that, with few exceptions, have been traditionally tackled separately. Moreover, it applies the lens of intersectionality to capture the layers of stratified discrimination that women and LGBTIAQ+ individuals may suffer from vis-à-vis their socioeconomic participation. In Europe, studies on intersectionality have mostly addressed the intersection of gender and work with regard to women and migration only, and, so far, little attention has been dedicated to the intersection of gender, ethnicity and work of LGBTIAQ+ individuals.</p> <p>InGEPaST positions itself in these scholarly lacunae and serves also as a socio-legal research vehicle to assess and promote the local application of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) nos. 5 (gender equality), 8 (decent work and economic growth), 10 (reduced inequalities), and 16</p>

	<p>(peace, justice and strong institutions) and of the three principles of universal values (human rights-based approach; leave no one behind; gender equality and women's empowerment).</p> <p>Research question(s)</p> <p>InGEPaST pursues the following research question (RQ):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how do gender and ethnicity intersect vis-à-vis socioeconomic participation (i.e., access to employment, education and social and public services) of women and LGBTIAQ+ individuals in South Tyrol and Catalonia in light of the SDGs (nos. 5, 8, 10, and 16) and the three principles of universal values? <p>This RQ is further articulated into the following research sub-questions (SRQs):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the main social drivers that influence the intersection of gender and ethnicity in the socioeconomic participation of women and LGBTIAQ+ individuals in South Tyrol and Catalonia? How do they correlate, operate and differentiate? 2. What are the pros and cons of the existing (pre-pandemic) South Tyrolean and Catalan policies toward gender and ethnic socioeconomic participation? Should they be reshaped, and, if so, how? 3. How can the substate application of recovery policies or other substate/local policies and instruments promote socioeconomic participation of women and LGBTIAQ+ individuals in a post-pandemic scenario in South Tyrol and Catalonia, also in light of the SDGs (nos. 5, 8, 10, and 16) and the three principles?
Funding body	Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen (I)
Project ID	Provincial Decree: 20771/2021 - CUP: D55F21004120003
Partner/hosting research centre	Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Faculty of Legal Sciences, Public Law Dept. (URV)
Date DMP created	2022-02-23
Date DPM (last) update	2022-05-12
Version	1.2
Name of researcher with responsibilities for data management	Dr. Alexandra Tomaselli (PI) ORCID: 0000-0001-7886-3912
Research Organization Registry (ROR)	Eurac Research: https://ror.org/01xt1w755

2 Data description and collection

InGEPaST collects and analyzes individual perceptions of gender and ethnic policies' stakeholders (women and LGBTIAQ+ individuals and their associations) as well as local policymakers and scrutinizes the level of application and impact of legal instruments (e.g., policies) upon these sectors of the society.

InGEPaST foresees to use three main qualitative research techniques by carrying out two rounds of semi-structured qualitative interviews, one round of (two or more) focus groups for each South Tyrol and Catalonia, and two content analysis. Other qualitative research approaches are not excluded a priori.¹

Therefore, InGEPaST uses two types of data:

1. primary data that are generated from approx. 60 (qualitative) semi-structured interviews and 4 focus groups (**data type A**),² and
2. secondary data, that are: scholarly articles of the project literature review; and the substate South Tyrolean and Catalan pre-pandemic and recovery policies and other instruments that deal with the socioeconomic participation, i.e., access to employment, education, and social and public services, of women and LGBTIAQ+ individuals (**data type B**).

2.1 Primary data (data type A)

Source of data: data collected individually by the project PI and project employed staff

Sub-types of data and sources of data:

A1: contact details of participants (informants/respondents)

A2: participants' categorization (personal data, incl. of special categories, e.g., on ethnic origins; reference to art. 9 EU Regulation 2016/679 - GDPR)

A3: interview data (raw data: recordings | elaborated data: notes, transcripts and NVivo coded data)

A4: focus groups data (raw data: recordings | elaborated data: notes, transcripts and NVivo coded data)

¹ See further in deliverable D.1.2 (WP1) "Short report on fine-tuned methodology", doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6531565.

² The number of interviews and focus groups may vary if participants (informants/respondents) are reticent to be interviewed or, vice versa, they provide other contacts that may serve as participants too (as according to the snowball quota criterion specified under "Data collection process"). Alternatively, if the number of interviews reduces, the focus groups will be increased. This has to be reevaluated in due time. See further in deliverable D.1.2 (WP1) "Short report on fine-tuned methodology", doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6531565.

Data collection process:

A1: these data are collected in accordance with InGEPaST sampling strategy that includes both the quota and the snowball samplings; therefore, contacts are retrieved from internet and social media (e.g., with regard to women and LGBTIAQ+ associations) but may also be provided by participants (informants/respondents) that may indicate other associations/civil society organizations and local policymakers to contact and serve as participants as well. If a participant decides to opt out the project, her/his data will be immediately destroyed.

A2: during the interviews and the focus groups, the informants/respondents are asked information about their name and surname, (ethnic) origins, mother tongue, gender, residence and domicile, geographical origins, and work and volunteering affiliations.

A3: audio and/or video recordings and notes of face-to-face or online interviews; the former are transcribed by ad hoc employed project staff, the latter are taken by the PI and/or ad hoc employed project staff; elaborated and coded data via NVivo.

A4: audio and/or video recordings and notes of face-to-face or online interviews; the former are transcribed by ad hoc employed project staff, the latter are taken by the PI and/or ad hoc employed project staff; elaborated and coded data via NVivo.

Particular character of data:

A1-A4 data contain not only personal but also special categories of personal data (e.g., on ethnic origins) in accordance with art. 9 EU Regulation 2016/679 – GDPR. They will be thus encrypted by using the VeraCrypt open-source software which ensures among the current highest levels of encryption. A1-A4 data will be stored in the VeraCrypt volume folder created on the PI of InGEPaST (myself) personal laptop, which is password protected. The password to mount the volume of VeraCrypt and thus access the encrypted file, will be stored via the KeyPass open-source software that protects the passwords. Another two VeraCrypt volumes will be created on an external hardisk and in the OneDrive/SharedPoint cloud provided by Eurac Research as a back-up (see also section 3.2). The passwords to mount these volumes will be also saved with KeyPass. The participants (informants/respondents) will be pseudonymized through a numerical or alphabetical code. Therefore, A1-A4 data will be stored in accordance with the same numerical or alphabetical code. The encryption key will be stored in the abovementioned VeraCrypt encrypted folder. Only the PI will have access to the VeraCrypt encrypted folder but may give temporary access by sharing the VeraCrypt password saved in KeyPass to access the OneDrive/SharedPoint backed-up folder to ad hoc project employed staff that is in charge of transcribing data A3-A4 and/or to the PI supervisors in case of unforeseen circumstances (see also sections 3 and 5.4).

Data type A1-A2 and the raw data of data A3-A4 (recordings) will be deleted after the completion of the project. The elaborated data (transcriptions and NVivo coded data) of data type A3-A4 will be retained up to 5 years after the completion of the project in accordance with the project information and privacy sheet that will be distributed to the participants (informants/respondents) and that will contain also the consent forms as specified below. After 5 years from the completion of the project, also elaborated A3-A4 data (transcriptions and NVivo coded data) will be destroyed with the exception of those metadata, datasets and project outputs that will be stored in an open access repository (see section 6).

Consent procedure:

Prior to data collection of data A2-A4, each informant/respondent will duly receive an information notice on InGEPaST that contains details about the project and its methodology, research techniques and results, and on the data protection and privacy and the processing of the participant's personal data

in accordance with EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), incl., art. 9 on special categories of personal data (such as those on ethnic origins). This information notice also includes the consent forms to participate voluntarily in the project, the right to withdraw from the project and revoke the consent, to the processing of the personal data (including, as mentioned, special categories such as those on the ethnic origins), and to allow the PI (myself) and/or the project employed staff to take video and sound recordings (when applicable) for transcription purposes. The information notice and the consent forms are elaborated in cooperation with Eurac Research Legal Office that ensures the respect of all national, European, and international laws. The PI of InGEPaST (myself) is responsible to hand in such information notice and collect signed consent forms from each participant before involving them in any project activity. Consent forms will be scanned and stored in the VeraCrypt encrypted folders and retained for 5 years after the end of the project in accordance with the project information and privacy sheet, after which date will be destroyed. If sent via email, the emails containing the consent form will be destroyed once stored the scanned file in the VeraCrypt folders. If any, consent hardcopies will be destroyed immediately after being scanned and stored them in the VeraCrypt folders.

2.2 Secondary data (data type B)

Source of data: open access articles or articles that may be retrieved via Eurac's or URV's libraries; online portals of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen and Generalitat Catalunya or other local public agencies; ad hoc emails to local civil servants dealing with access to employment, education, and social and public services of women and LGBTIAQ+.

Sub-types of data and sources of data:

B1: scholarly articles of the project literature review on intersectionality, ethnicity, women, LGBTIAQ+ and the intersection with work, employment, access to education, access to social and public services, and other social factors

B2: substate South Tyrolean and Catalan pre-pandemic and recovery policies and other instruments that deal with the socioeconomic participation, i.e., access to employment, education, and social and public services, of women and LGBTIAQ+ individuals

Accessing data:

B1: the scientific articles that will compose the literature review are accessed either freely if they are for free open access or freely readable online or retrieved via the libraries of Eurac and URV; emails may be sent to articles' authors if none of these possibilities is available to kindly ask them to share their articles with me for the InGEPaST research purposes.

B2: Policies normally take the form of ad hoc documents that are freely downloadable, but they may also be published online on the webpages of local administrations or, although rarely, be available only in hardcopy. For the latter, emails may be sent to local civil servants to request a scanned copy.

Data collection process and exporting output: both data type B1-B2 (mainly in the form of documents and webpages) will be downloaded in the PI's laptop project folder to be analyzed via the technique of content analysis by coding through the software NVivo.

Particular character of data: not applicable since neither published scientific articles policies nor public official documents usually contain personal data.

2.3 Format and size of data

Type of data	Format	Software	Estimated size	Specific character
Primary data (data type A)				
A1	.csv	Excel	100 kb	Personal data as per GDPR
A2	.csv	Excel	100 kb	Personal data, incl., special categories of personal data (e.g., on ethnic origins) in accordance with art. 9 GDPR
A3 (raw data: recordings; elaborated data: notes, transcripts and NVivo coded data)	.mp3 .mp4 .pdf .rtf .txt .nvp	PC, zoom or other recorders NVivo	30 GB (estimate of 60 one-hour interviews of 500MB each)	May contain personal data, including of special categories, relevant for analysis
A4 (raw data: recordings; elaborated data: notes, transcripts and NVivo coded data)	.mp3 .mp4 .pdf .rtf .txt .nvp	PC, zoom or other recorders External Eurac/own camera NVivo	5 GB (estimate of 4 2-hour focus groups of 1GB each)	May contain personal data, including of special categories, relevant for analysis
Secondary data (data type B)				
B1	.pdf .rtf .txt .odt .xhtml .htm	Word Adobe reader	20 GB	They do not contain personal data
B2	.pdf .rtf .txt .odt .xhtml .htm	Word Adobe reader	25 GB	They do not contain personal data
<i>Estimated total space required</i>			80 GB	

Table 1: Format and size of data of InGEPaST (PI/author own elaboration)

3 Data storage and back-up

3.1 Data pseudonymization and anonymization

Each participant (informant/respondent) will be pseudonymized through a numerical or alphabetical code. Therefore, A1-A4 data will be stored in accordance with the same numerical or alphabetical code. The encryption key will be stored in a VeraCrypt encrypted folder saved on the PI's laptop (that is password protected) as mentioned in section 2.1. Only the PI will have access to the project folders but may give temporary access to the VeraCrypt encrypted folder that contain A1-A4 data by sharing the VeraCrypt password saved in KeyPass of the OneDrive/SharePoint backed-up encrypted folder to the ad hoc project employed staff that is in charge of transcribing data A3-A4 and/or to the PI supervisors in case of unforeseen circumstances (see also section 5.4).

A selection of key interviews (part of data A3) and all the focus groups' transcripts (part of data A4) will be fully anonymized. Deidentification and anonymization will be done manually by the PI (myself). This is possible because the number of selected interviews to be fully anonymized and deidentified will be not more than 10 and the focus groups not more than 4. This is why these are the only datasets that will be shared in an open access repository (see section 6.1).

3.2 Storage and back-up

All data will be stored on the PI's laptop, which is password protected (primary storage), and backed-up on an external hard disk (secondary storage) every two days. Every two days data type A 1-A4 will be backed-up also on the OneDrive/SharePoint cloud provided by Eurac Research (thirdly storage), which does automatic back-ups daily. Since the OneDrive/SharePoint cloud does not allow to create a folder bigger than 10GB (its current size), only data type A1-A4, and, out of these, only audio files of interviews and focus groups, will be backed-up on it and its encrypted folder.

Both the hard disk and the OneDrive/SharePoint cloud back-ups are saved in encrypted folders (VeraCrypt volumes, see section 2.1 above), and the passwords to access these volumes will be stored on KeyPass.

The NVivo coded A3-A4 data will be also saved in the VeraCrypt encrypted folder on the PI's laptop and will also be backed-up in the hard disk and the OneDriveSharePoint cloud encrypted folders every two days.

3.3 Folder structures and file naming

Folders will be organized organically per type of data and the titles will be short and concise and of immediate understanding, as follows. Subfolders nos. a-e will be stored in the VeraCrypt encrypted folders (PI's laptop, and backed-up on a hard disk and OneDriveSharePoint cloud encrypted folders):

1. VeraCrypt encrypted folder – folder name "1_EncryptedData":
 - a. Consent forms of participants – folder name "a_ConsentForms"

- b. Tables and/or other files related to contact details (data type A1) and personal and sensitive data (data type A2) – folder name: “b_DataA1&A2”;
 - c. Data types A3 and A4 raw data (e.g., audio files) – folder name “c_RawDataA3&A4”;
 - d. Data types A3 and A4 raw data transcripts (i.e., transcripts of interviews and focus groups) – folder name “d_TranscriptsInterviews&FG”
 - e. Table with the encryption key – folder name “e_EncryptionKey”
2. Data types A3-A4 anonymized and deidentified data (i.e., anonymized and deidentified transcripts of a selection of key interviews and of the focus groups) – folder name “2_AnonymizedTranscriptsInt&FG”;
 3. Data type B1 – folder name “3_DataB1_LiteratureReview”
 4. Data type B2 – folder name “4_DataB2_PoliciesEtAl”

All folder files will contain a ReadMe file (.txt) that will explain what the type of data that the folder contains and how files are organized.

There will be maximum 4-level folders within the project project folder, e.g.:
InGEPaSTproject\1_EncryptedData\c_RawDataA3&A4\A3-InterviewsAudio.

Subfolders will make a direct reference to the type of data contained therein (e.g., A3-InterviewsAudio).

The files will be named with the numerical code of the interview and the date of the interview following the convention of YYYYMMDD (e.g., Interview1_20220520). This standardized file naming will guarantee that each file will have a unique name that is easily recognizable and thus interoperable.

4 Data documentation

4.1 Data consistency and quality control

As mentioned in section 2.1, InGEPaST uses a purposive (non-probability) sampling strategy that includes both the quota and the snowball samplings to find and recruit the participants (informants/respondents) to collect data A1-A4. The reason to use the quota sampling is to offer results that, albeit won't be statistically representative, will anyhow offer an indication of the real-life experiences of women and LGBTIAQ+ vis-à-vis their access to employment, education, and social and public services in South Tyrol and Catalonia.³ This shall provide data consistency.

In addition, participants (informants/respondents) will be given the possibility to validate the transcripts of data A3-A4 and thus ensure data quality control.

³ For details, see in deliverable D.1.2 (WP1) “Short report on fine-tuned methodology”, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6531565.

4.2 Metadata

All the metadata will be created according to the [Dublin Core Metadata Initiative](#) and will include the 15 metadata elements foreseen by the Dublin Core schema. The metadata will be generated by using an Excel file or the online [Dublin Core Metadata Generator](#).

4.3 Data identifiers

The metadata, datasets and project outputs that will be shared on an open access repository (see below section 6.1) will be assigned a DOI.

Data type A2-A4 will be stored in accordance with the specific numerical or alphabetical codes that will be assigned to and pseudonymize each participant (informant/respondent) (see sections 2.1 and 3.1). The encryption key will be stored in the VeraCrypt encrypted folder.

Other project outputs (e.g., scientific and blog articles) will also be assigned a DOI.

5 Data access

5.1 Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

I, as the PI of the InGEPaST project, abide to the Eurac Research rules on IPR and I am conscious that the project generated data belong to Eurac Research.

At any time, any informant/respondent has the right to request access to their personal data, and to correct or delete that data, or to limit its processing. In addition, the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority. When the data processing is based on consent, the data subject has the right to withdraw that consent at any time. The data subject may also exercise all other rights pursuant to current data protection regulations (art. 15 et seq. GDPR) by writing to the e-mail address: privacy@eurac.edu.

5.2 Restriction on data access during the project

As mentioned, InGEPaST deals with a variety of personal data, some of which belong to special categories as per art. 9 of the GDPR. Hence, data access will be restricted during the project to myself (the PI), the project staff that may be employed to transcribe data type A3 and A4 and/or to my supervisors at Eurac Research in case of unforeseen circumstances (see below section 5.4).

5.3 Control of data access

All data type A (A1-A4) will be stored in a VeraCrypt encrypted folder created on the PI of InGEPaST (myself) personal laptop, which is password protected. The password to mount the volume of VeraCrypt and thus access the encrypted file will be stored via the KeyPass open-source software that protects the passwords. Once encrypted, they will be also copied on an external hardisk and in a OneDrive/SharedPoint cloud folder provided by Eurac Research as a back-up (see section 3.2; see also sections 2.1 and 3.2). Only the PI will have access to the project folders but may give temporary access to VeraCrypt encrypted folder on OneDrive/SharedPoint to ad hoc project employed staff that is in charge of transcribing data A3-A4 and/or to my supervisors at Eurac Research in case of unforeseen circumstances (see below section 5.4).

5.4 Data access in case of illness, staff changes, etc.

In case of unforeseen circumstances, the PI's supervisors at Eurac Research (Institute for Minority Rights), namely Günther Rautz and Alice Engl may access to data type A1-A4 in the VeraCrypt folder on OneDrive/sharedPoint since the VeraCrypt password will be shared with them via KeyPass. This has been agreed with Günther Rautz and Alice Engl on 23 March 2022, and with [Eurac Research Information Technologies](#) (IT) during the meeting of 5 April 2022.

5.5 Data access after the end of the project

I (the PI) have a permanent contract with Eurac Research (Institute for Minority Rights) and I am likely to re-use part of collected data after the end of the project and up to 5 years until when elaborated A3-A4 data will be retained. This will be specified in the project and privacy information sheet and will be expressively asked to the participants in the consent forms. InGEPaSt will share its metadata and part of its datasets and other project outputs as specified in section 6.1 and table 2 below.

6 Data sharing and preservation

6.1 Data sharing

InGEPaST will share all those generated metadata, datasets and other project outputs that can guarantee deidentification and anonymization and the respect of the privacy of the participants (informants/respondents) in accordance with the EU GDPR.

In particular, InGEPaST will openly share on an open access repository (namely, Zenodo) its metadata and part of its datasets and other project outputs as specified in the table 2 below.

The choice of Zenodo is based on the following: it is free and supports open science; Zenodo has 50GB size limit which shall suffice for the above-mentioned metadata, datasets and other project outputs that will be shared; it provides DOI and links files with the author via ORCID; Creative Commons license (e.g., CC-BY) are available; it supports a variety of metadata schemes; it is non-profit.

Type of data	Shared on Zenodo (yes/no)	Reasons for sharing or not sharing
Primary data (data type A)		
A1	No	Privacy and safety of participants (informants/respondents)
A2	No	Privacy and safety of participants (informants/respondents)
A3 raw data (recordings)	No	Privacy and safety of participants (informants/respondents). Raw data type A3 cannot be shared since they contain personal data, including those of special categories (art. 9 GDPR).
A3 elaborated data (notes, transcripts and NVivo coded data)	No	All data type A3 (interviews) notes and transcripts cannot be made open accessible due to confidentiality and privacy concerns since so many transcripts are not amenable to be totally deidentified and anonymized. Moreover, resources have not been budgeted to contract a repository that ensures total deidentification and anonymization such as QualiService. However, the transcripts of a selection of key interviews will be shared openly as specified below.
A3 elaborated data (selection of up to 10 key interviews)	Yes	The transcripts of up to 10 key interviews (part of data type A3) will be deidentified and anonymized by myself, the PI, and will be thus shared on the open access repository Zenodo.
A3 NVivo list of codes	Yes	Scientific reuse and FAIR principles (see section 6.2)
A4 raw data (recording)	No	Privacy and safety of participants (informants/respondents). Raw data type A4 cannot be shared since they contain personal data, including those of special categories (art. 9 GDPR).
A4 elaborated data (notes and NVivo coded data)	No	Privacy and safety of participants (informants/respondents). Data type A4 (focus groups) notes and NVivo coded data cannot be deidentified.
A4 elaborated data (transcripts)	Yes	Data type A4 (focus groups) transcripts may be deidentified and anonymized manually by myself, the PI, and will be thus shared on the open access repository Zenodo.
A4 NVivo list of codes	Yes	Scientific reuse and FAIR principles (see section 6.2)

Secondary data (data type B)		
B1 (metadata catalogue)	Yes	Scientific reuse and FAIR principles (see section 6.2)
B2 (metadata catalogue)	Yes	Scientific reuse and FAIR principles (see section 6.2)
Other project outputs		
InGEPaST deliverable D.1.2 (WP1) "Short report on fine-tuned methodology", doi:10.5281/zenodo.6531565	Yes	Scientific reuse and FAIR principles (see section 6.2)
InGEPaST present deliverable D.1.1 "Research Data Management Plan", doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6531621	Yes	Scientific reuse and FAIR principles (see section 6.2)

Table 2: Data sharing of InGEPaST (PI/author own elaboration)

6.2 FAIR principles

InGEPaST abides to the EU [FAIR principles](#). The metadata, datasets and other project outputs will be

- **findable** since they are available and findable through an open access repository (Zenodo), they will all assigned a DOI and linked to the author (myself) via ORCID;
- **accessible** because duly described with metadata that follow the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative;
- **interoperable** because they will be available in standard/open formats as specified above (see section 2.3);
- **reusable** because they are richly described and will use a Creative Commons license (e.g., CC-BY).

6.3 Criteria for long-term preservation

The metadata, datasets and other project outputs that will be preserved long-term and be shared follow three criteria:

- Compliance with confidentiality and privacy commitments as well as with what the participant has given her/his consent for;
- Total deidentification and anonymization;
- Reuse value for the scientific community.

7 Resources and responsibilities

7.1 Cost for data collection and documentation

Data type A1-A4 will be acquired by myself, the PI, while additional project staff will be employed for both data collection and transcriptions. Personnel costs related to these activities have been budgeted and funded.

Costs for printing documents and other office related costs are covered by the Eurac Research or the partner/hosting research centre URV.

Data type B1 are retrieved either via free open access, Eurac research and URV libraries or emails to authors; data type B2 are usually available online or shall be provided after contacting local civil servants via email. Hence, they imply no cost apart from those personnel costs that have been also budgeted and funded.

7.2 Cost for data storage and data access and security

The PI's laptop and the OneDrive/SharedPoint cloud storage are provided by Eurac Research. The hard disk is already of property of the PI. Thus, they do not imply any cost. Eurac Research IT provides help for setting up the data access and security protocols.

7.3 Cost for data preservation, availability and reuse

The files will be immediately stored in standard/open formats (see above section 2.3) to avoid delays and costs of file conversion. In this way, those metadata, datasets and other project outputs that will be shared will be already in an interoperable file formats.

Zenodo is a free repository and implies no costs and freely allows the use of those metadata, datasets and other project outputs that will be shared on it.

Thanks

The author is extremely grateful to Liise Lehtsalu (RSO, Eurac Research) for her invaluable guidance and her suggestions on this as well as earlier versions of this text; to Eurac Research IT for their kind assistance; and to Víctor Merino Sancho (URV), Alice Engl and Günther Rautz (Eurac Research) for their comments and kind supervision.